

Logging Shell User Activity

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2015 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20150604> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

In some environments, it is mandatory to keep track of every user activity on a specific system. Since in most cases the systems are certified, we searched for a solution running on a RHEL 6, no patched kernel, and no unsupported hack.

Figure: Red Hat Enterprise Linux

We evaluated some solutions, but not one is really satisfying.

3. Problem

The problem is pretty simple: a legitimate user logs into a system using ssh or console and starts a shell; we want to keep track of all the commands he executes on the system. It should be impossible for the *unprivileged user* to bypass the audit mechanism. It should be hard, or at least there must be a notice for the *superuser* to bypass or tamper the audit mechanism.

4. Solutions

Some solutions (in form of scripts, *bash* functions, pipes and so on) can be *dducked* [1] and may function in some way, but all have some limitations; specifically, the solutions using *bash functions* or rewritten *PROMPT* may be manipulated or unset by the *unprivileged user*.

After some testing, we decided to take a closer look at following tools:

- auditd
- rootsh

- pam_tty_audit.so
- sudo

4.1. auditd

auditd [2] is the userspace component to the Linux Auditing System. It's responsible for writing audit records to the disk. Of particular interest is the option *-S* (track a *SYSCALL*), specifically the syscall *EXECVE*. We added two rules to *auditd.conf*, tagging *unprivileged user* and *privileged user* activities differently.

auditd policy:

```
# logging_bash_commands
-a exit,always -F arch=b64 -F euid=0 -S
execve -k rootact
-a exit,always -F arch=b32 -F euid=0 -S
execve -k rootact
-a exit,always -F arch=b64 -F euid>=1000 -S
execve -k useract
-a exit,always -F arch=b32 -F euid>=1000 -S
execve -k useract
```

auditd is not really a tool to track shell activity, it is very verbose, logs a log of details and must be carefully configured since impacts hard on system performance.

The biggest issues are the command parameters logged on a separate line:

- *SYSCALL* line for the user parameters
- *EXECVE* for the command and command parameters

On the other side, we can audit user activity very well and use standard components (*aureport* [3]), to search and report the audit log. As example, if a user executes a command:

```
[admin@mos ~]$ ls -lisa
```

The corresponding *auditd* log shows:

```
[root@mos pam.d]# aureport --tty -ts today
...
type=SYSCALL msg=audit(1432238948.640:38103):
arch=c000003e syscall=59 success=yes exit=0
a0=1124430 a1=11289c0 a2=112de40
a3=7fffcf153270 items=2 ppid=13513 pid=16214
aid=1000 uid=1000 gid=1000 euid=1000
suid=1000 fsuid=1000 egid=1000 sgid=1000
fsgid=1000 tty=pts3 ses=19 comm="ls"
exe="/bin/ls"
subj=unconfined_u:unconfined_r:unconfined_t:s
0-s0:c0.c1023 key="useract"
```


6. External Links

[1] https://duckduckgo.com/?q=log+_bash+_commands&ia=qa

[2] <http://linux.die.net/man/8/auditd>

[3] <http://linux.die.net/man/8/aureport>

[4] <http://linux.die.net/man/1/rootsh>

[5] http://linux.die.net/man/8/pam_tty_audit

[6] <http://www.sudo.ws>